

JOURNAL
OF THE
INDIAN CHEMICAL SOCIETY

**Potentiometric Estimation of Copper with
Sodium Sulphide.**

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The possibility of the potentiometric estimation of copper with sodium sulphide has been shown by Jha (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 10, 41). The titrations were carried on with copper sulphate solutions containing a measured amount of acetic acid. It was also shown in the paper quoted above that for correct estimations the *regulation of the quantity of free acetic acid* is of considerable importance.

The titrations described in this paper were conducted with copper sulphate dissolved in buffer solutions with a view to (i) obviate the necessity of prejudging the amount of free acetic acid to be added to copper sulphate solutions, as required by the method already quoted, and to (ii) obtain complete titration curves under constant hydrogen ion concentrations as far as possible.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Copper in the form of copper sulphate was dissolved in buffer solutions. The hydrogen ion concentrations of the buffer solutions before dissolving the copper sulphate as well as afterwards, was determined electrometrically. There was very little difference in the hydrogen ion concentrations subsequently when copper sulphate was present.

Fig. 1. Vol. required to complete the titration 17.6 c.c., p_H 3.7

Fig. 2. " " " " 17.26 c.c., p_H 3.0

Fig. 3. " " " " 21.3 c.c., p_H 5.54

Titration were done with CuSO_4 in $\text{CH}_3\text{COONa}-\text{CH}_3\text{COOH}$ buffer soln.

Sodium sulphide solution.—In order to get quantitative agreement between the precipitant and the copper sulphate to be titrated, sodium sulphide was freed from the sulphite, etc., by acidification and subsequent neutralisation (*loc. cit.*) till the solution was neutral to litmus. At this stage the solution contained mostly free hydrogen sulphide.

From the titration curves shown in Figs. 1-3, it is clear that upto a considerable distance from the beginning of the titrations there is no regularity in the *e.m.f.* variations which may take any form, although the completeness of the titrations is always marked with a sudden drop in potential. The potentials at the end point are found to rise with p_H as shown in Table I.

At present no explanation is available either to the irregularities observed in the *e.m.f.* changes in the beginning or to the rise in the end-point potentials with p_H .

Some of the results of the titrations are shown in Table II. It will be seen that the most suitable range for making up the copper sulphate solutions is between p_H 3 to p_H 6. Above p_H 6, the error rises rapidly.

TABLE I.

p_H of the buffer in which CuSO_4 solns. were made	3.7	5.0	5.5	5.9	6.1
Average value of potentials at the end against sat. calomel electrode (volts)	0.063	0.07	0.083	0.097	0.100

TABLE II.

p_H	Strength of CuSO_4 soln.	Actual amount of $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$.	$\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ found by potentiometric titrations.	Error.
2.99	<i>M</i> /121.26	2.059 g./litre	2.059	0.0%
	<i>M</i> /148.62	1.680	1.685	0.3
3.73	<i>M</i> /121.6	2.059	2.065	0.3
	<i>M</i> /148.62	1.6800	1.672	0.6
4.30	<i>M</i> /18.223	13.702	13.728	0.2
	<i>M</i> /29.160	8.5800	8.576	0.2
5.0	<i>M</i> /264.00	0.9455	0.9500	0.5
	<i>M</i> /312.60	0.7987	0.8044	0.8
5.90	<i>M</i> /183.92	1.3580	0.3650	0.6
	<i>M</i> /250.9	0.9992	0.9995	0.03
6.09	<i>M</i> /187.46	1.332	1.348	1.2
6.11	<i>M</i> /244.40	1.022	1.045	2.25

SUMMARY.

1. The estimation of copper in the form of copper sulphate in sodium acetate acetic acid buffers can be carried on without adding any free acid. This obviates the judging of the proper amount of acid to be added before titrations. The best p_H range for the buffers to make up copper sulphate solutions is between 3—5.

2. The potentials at the end point have been found to rise with p_H .

Our thanks are due to Profs. H. Krall and B. L. Vaish for their interest in the work.